

A STUDY ON EFFICACY AND CHALLENGES OF INTERNSHIP PROGRAMME IN TEACHER EDUCATION

Dr. G.M. SUNAGAR

Asst. Professor, Vijayanagar College of Education and P.G. Centre of Studies in Education,
Vidyanagar, Hubballi-31, Karnataka.

Email: girishsunagar@yahoo.co.in

ABSTRACT

Internship programme in teacher education is very important to shape the trainees into an effective teacher of tomorrow. It provides not only practice teaching but opportunities to participate in activities of the school like a regular teacher. In the review of the NPE 1986 observed that an internship model for teacher training should be adopted because the internship model is firmly based on the primary value of actual field experience in a realistic situation, on the development of teaching skills by practice over a period of time. If we think about the internship programme of our teacher education colleges, certain questions arise in our mind. Do our trainees involve in all activities of the schools? Do teacher educators evaluate internship programme in well manner? To get answers of these questions present study was carried out. The main objective was to study the opinions of teacher educators and pre-service teachers with respect to internship programme. For the present study five teacher education colleges were randomly selected and from each college five teacher educators and twenty pre-service teachers were selected using random sampling technique. Result reveals that for improvement in internship programme we should consider all 3 stages - (1) Pre-internship (2) Internship (3) Post-internship for evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

Teachers are not born but they can be made by teacher education. In the recent years all over India there has been a drastic changes in teacher education course. Practicum approach adopted in the modern teacher education course is to place a student teacher in a classroom situation under the supervision of a qualified teacher. The concept of Internship introduced in the two year teacher education program throughout the country is quite challenging one for all the teacher education institutions. The aim of internship program is to incorporate teaching skills among the student

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

teachers. Internship program is an effective way to give training to the student-teachers about real world of work. It give them an opportunity to integrate theory and practice, plan and deliver lesson properly, critically analyze their own and peers teaching style and improve them in the light of feedback given by supervisors. Through this program they understand the role and responsibilities of professional teachers. Teacher education is divided into pre-service teacher education programme and in-service teacher education programme. Internship is an important component of pre-service teacher education programme to provide field experience to the trainees. It provides not only practice teaching but opportunities to participate in activities of the school like a regular teacher. Internship programme has the following components.1.Visits to Innovative Centres of Pedagogy and Learning.2. Action research.3.Developing Unit Plans in advance than teaching.4.Creating and maintaining resources for teaching-learning in the internship schools. 5. Co-curricular activities. In teacher education internship has three stages. (1) Pre-internship,(2) Internship, (3) Post-internship. The pre-internship activities include selecting school for the internship, making groups of trainees, arrange time table, write unit plan, planning of activities ect. The internship is a field experience for trainees, which includes practice teaching and all activities of the school. The post-internship activities cover final report of internship and evaluation.

IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

We know that if internship programme is done with complete involvement of trainees, it may be useful in evaluating teacher’s ability. It supports socialization within the profession, stimulates development of teaching-learning concepts, provides a protected field of experimentation, allows insight into new perspectives and enhances motivation to continue learning and reflecting. Internship would help trainees to choose, design, organize and conduct meaningful classroom activities, critically reflect upon their own practices through observations, record keeping and analysis and develop strategies for evaluating students’ learning for feedback into curriculum and pedagogic practice. If we think about the situation of our teacher education colleges, certain questions arise in our mind. Does our internship programme include such types of components? Do our trainees involve in all activities of the schools? Do teacher educators evaluate internship programme in well manner? To get answers of these questions, this study was carried out.

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

OPERATIONAL DEFINATIONS

Teacher Educators: The Teacher Educators are those who are qualified with the degree of Masters of Education engaged in training the students who have joined the B.Ed. colleges with the aim of becoming a teacher.

Pre-service Teachers: Pre–service Teachers are those students of B.Ed. colleges who have joined the institution to be trained to become a successful teacher in future.

Internship Programme: Student teachers stay for full day in the schools during the working hours and participate in the school processes is called internship programme.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of the present study is to study the opinions of teacher educators and pre-service teachers with respect to following components of internship programme.

- Evaluation of student performance
- practice teaching
- Participating in school activities
- Observing lessons of the peers
- Conducting action research
- Organizing co-curricular activities in the school
- Visits to Innovative Centres of Pedagogy and Learning.
- Maintaining the diary
- Writing a report of the internship

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The descriptive survey method was used to study the Opinion of Teacher Educators and Pre-service Teachers of teacher education colleges affiliated with Karnataka University Dharwad about internship programme.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

In the current study the population represents the teacher educators and pre-service teachers (2017-19) of teacher education colleges of Karnataka University Dharwad.

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

For the current study five teacher education colleges were randomly selected and from each college five teacher educators and twenty pre-service teachers were selected using random sampling technique. Sample has twenty five teacher educators and hundred pre-service teachers.

TOOL OF THE STUDY

For data collection researcher has used self made questionnaire on internship programme for teacher educators and pre-service teachers.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- ❖ Internship provides an opportunity to critically reflect and improve on lesson practice.
- ❖ Trainees maintain a diary during the internship so they have day-wise record of all the activities carried out during the internship.
- ❖ Lack of support in terms of materials and equipments in the schools.
- ❖ Some colleges visited to BRC CRC DIET and Special schools also they came to know that the functions of the institutions.
- ❖ Trainees are administer a unit test by using blue print; they know the actual process of evaluation.
- ❖ Trainees took guidance from teachers and principals of the schools about CRC, time table and different types of registers.
- ❖ In karnatak University affiliated teacher education colleges pre-service teachers took 24 (12+12) classes during internship & got marks for each class out of less than two marks only. So they were not serious about their classes during internship.
- ❖ Trainees did not meet teachers to learn class room management techniques.
- ❖ Most of the time the teaching of trainees was not observed during the internship.
- ❖ Principals did not involve in trainees examination and evaluation work during internship. Trainees did not develop rapport between school principal and teachers.
- ❖ Trainees did not write lesson plans & make teaching aids in advance & did not get approval from teacher educators.
- ❖ In some schools principals and teachers suggested their topics to trainees for teaching so they could not follow their lesson plans during internship.
- ❖ Trainees did not observe classes of school teachers, because some school teacher were not

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

give permission and there is no mark of observation.

- ❖ Trainees did not conduct remedial classes in school during internship.
- ❖ During internship trainees observed classes of their peer. They did not discuss about the strengths & weaknesses of a class room & the teacher.
- ❖ Trainees can not judge the competence of a teacher just by observing a lesson.
- ❖ Trainees did not conduct action research in school during internship.
- ❖ Trainees did not conduct remedial classes in school during internship.
- ❖ Trainees submitted their report to their coordinator after internship but did not present it in assembly.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

- ❖ Trainees have to maintain diary, it will enable them to take stock of the situation and plan future course of actions.
- ❖ Trainees should take remedial teaching, conduct test and analyze the result and give suggestions for improving performance of the students. Thus they can understand the actual process of evaluation & learn how to evaluate the students in the school.
- ❖ We should give real experience of different works as examinations, evaluations, event management...etc. to pre-service teachers. This experience leads them to be better organizer once they become full-time teachers.
- ❖ It is necessary to see that the teaching of trainees must be observed at least by one of the teaching staff of the school.
- ❖ Trainees should complete practice teaching within the prescribed duration & write lesson plan, prepare teaching aid in advance & get approval from method master. They should check students' lesson plan properly.
- ❖ Trainees should conduct different activities in the school so they can understand about the process & difficulties involved in organizing the activities.
- ❖ To give practical experience of conducting action research to trainees, action research must be a part of the internship programme. So trainees can identify a problem & find solution to the problem through action research.
- ❖ Internship is very long process with many activities; it has 3 stages, so we should consider all 3 stages for evaluation. We should include practice teaching, observation record,

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

evaluation record, preparation & presentation of teaching aids, record of participation in school activities & presentation of internship report for evaluation.

- ❖ For improvement in internship programme in future, post-internship is very important. In presence of all trainees and teacher educators a group leader should present a brief report of internship and all members should discuss on various aspects of internship.

CONCLUSION

Internship program also give them opportunity to understand different aspects of school program and improve their skills and abilities in teaching profession. An effective and improved internship program is required in developing student-teachers personalities as true professionals in the field of education. so we should make it more fruitful by our serious efforts. It should not for just completion of teacher education programme but it must be for making successful and effective teacher. We have to adopt certain strategy for quality improvement in internship programme.

REFERENCES

- Ahuja,A.(2007).Educational management Planning and finance. (First edition). New Delhi: Authors press.
- Parkash, R.(Editor).(2007).Teachers for better schools .(first edition).New Delhi: Alfa publications.
- Roberts, A. 2000. Mentoring revisited: A phenomenological reading of the literature, Mentoring and Tutoring, 8(2), pp. 145–170.
- Sharma, R. (Editor).(2007).Development of education system in India.(first edition).New delhi: Alfa publications.
- https://www.academia.edu/7710793/Internship_Programme_in_Teacher_Education
- <http://www.unesdoc.unesco.org/image/0016/001627/162798e.pdf>
